

Integrating Digital Twins into Evolutionary Optimization of Factory Layouts

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ABSTRACT

Efficient production processes are essential for the competitiveness of manufacturing enterprises, with the spatial layout of production units playing a key role in material flow efficiency, space utilization, and overall production costs. This challenge is formalized as the Facility Layout Problem (FLP), a nonlinear combinatorial optimization task aimed at determining efficient arrangements of non-overlapping production units under various constraints. Traditional FLP approaches typically rely on static evaluation models, which provide only coarse performance estimates and fail to capture the dynamic behavior of real production systems. To address this limitation, this paper proposes a novel framework that integrates a multi-objective evolutionary algorithm with digital twin simulations. Candidate layouts are evaluated through a two-stage process that combines feasibility checks with detailed performance assessment using automatically generated and executed digital twin models. The framework enables asynchronous, fully automated exploration of layout alternatives without human intervention and supports sector-wise workstation allocation constraints reflecting technological requirements. The proposed approach is validated on a real-world-inspired production system involving two product types, eight types of production units, and multi-step process plans with repeated workstation visits. Experimental results demonstrate that the framework can efficiently generate high-performing layouts while requiring only a limited number of simulations.

CCS CONCEPTS

• **Computing methodologies** → **Genetic algorithms; Simulation tools.**

KEYWORDS

Multi-objective optimization, Digital twins, Evolutionary algorithms

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1 INTRODUCTION

For any manufacturing enterprise, the high efficiency of its processes is a crucial factor determining its competitiveness [5, 22]. One of the key processes is the production of the company's product portfolio, which is carried out by its production system. Within the production system, we can identify both value-adding and non-value-adding processes, or more specifically, we can distinguish between technological and non-technological operations. Value-adding processes are primarily those that transform inputs into outputs through a series of steps, using dedicated technological equipment and human labor. Non-technological operations primarily include material and product handling, storage, inspection, and similar activities that do not directly create value, but are necessary for delivering the final product. Both of these groups of processes are associated with costs that need to be minimized. Non-technological operations related to the handling of inputs, parts, and products between individual workstations and storage areas are highly dependent on the spatial layout of the production system, which is a key factor influencing material flow and its efficiency. Similarly, the spatial arrangement of production is a crucial factor determining the efficiency of space utilization which considers the effectiveness of the area or volume occupied by the production system relative to its performance and the overall production costs. Thus, the optimal placement of production units within the factory premises is a key challenge in production management and industrial engineering.

Finding the optimal arrangement of production units (both the location and orientation of the production units) within the area available is well known as the Facility Layout Problem (FLP) [10, 16, 24]. Formally, it is a nonlinear combinatorial optimization problem aiming at determining the most efficient arrangement of non-overlapping facilities on a factory floor while meeting specific objectives subject to various constraints.

Evaluation criteria for FLP are quantitative and qualitative. Common quantitative criteria include maximizing area utilization; minimizing costs related to construction, structural, or technological modifications of the production space; minimizing material-handling costs; and minimizing flow intensity, which depends on both the frequency of transports and the transportation distance between collaborating production units. Among the qualitative criteria are often aspects that are difficult to quantify, such as enhancing the ability to visually monitor the entire area or specific sectors, and improving workplace safety. These criteria are beyond the scope of this paper.

Typically, when solving FLP, optimization criteria are evaluated based on a static model of the spatial arrangement of the production units. However, for the production system optimization purposes,

the performance criteria calculated using such a static model provide only a very rough estimate of how good or bad the given layout is.

Digital twins (DT) have become a significant phenomenon in recent years, penetrating various fields [23]. One of their key application areas is naturally the simulation of manufacturing and logistics processes in production enterprises. A digital twin is implemented using dedicated simulation tools, which serve as a crucial component for the optimization and planning of manufacturing and logistics processes. With these tools, we can model, analyze, and simulate various aspects of production lines, storage operations, supply chains, product mix, and more, providing deeper insights into the production system represented by the given layout.

One of the leading simulation tools is Tecnomatix Plant Simulation [21], which focuses on industrial processes, particularly manufacturing and logistics. This software enables users to create detailed models that capture all aspects of the production system, allowing for the evaluation of operational performance, identification of bottlenecks, exploration of various logistics strategies, visualization and animation of processes, and comprehensive data analysis.

The design of a production system is typically a highly labor-intensive process that requires close collaboration among experts from various departments within the company, such as production, technology, maintenance, quality control, safety, logistics, and others. These specialists work together to develop a specific production layout or several design variants, which are then evaluated. Promising design variants can be further developed into virtual twins, which enable the evaluation of key dynamic parameters corresponding to the given layout. Naturally, this is a highly demanding iterative process, and only a limited number of candidate layouts can typically be created and fine-tuned.

The main challenge addressed in this work is to develop a tool that automatically integrates digital twin simulations into the process of finding optimal factory layouts. We propose a framework that integrates a multi-objective evolutionary algorithm with Tecnomatix Plant Simulation (hereafter referred to as `PlantSim`) to solve the Facility Layout Problem. The evolutionary algorithm maintains a population of candidate solutions, whose quality is assessed through a two-stage evaluation process. First, each solution is checked for feasibility and assigned a coarse quality score. Only valid floorplans proceed to the second stage, where their performance is evaluated based on a simulation of the production process within a digital twin. Importantly, a digital twin is automatically generated and executed for each specific candidate floorplan. In this way, the computation converges toward a set of valid solutions whose production line arrangements result in high values of the monitored performance metrics – all without requiring any interaction with a human expert.

The proposed method is tested on a use case based on a real production system designed to process two types of products, which pass through eight types of production units. The technological process consists of 10 and 14 steps, respectively, with certain production units being revisited multiple times. We also demonstrate the use of a sector-wise production unit allocation constraint, in which each production unit can be placed in only one sector from a predefined set of allowed sectors. Such constraints are common

in real-world manufacturing settings, where a given production line may be located only in a sector that meets its technological requirements.

The main contributions of this paper are summarized as follows:

- (1) Design of an optimization framework for the generation of well-performing layouts for manufacturing and logistics processes in production enterprises using a multi-objective optimization approach, hybridizing an evolutionary algorithm with digital twin simulations.
- (2) Introduction of sector-wise production unit allocation constraints, where each production unit can be placed only to specified sector(s) within the factory.
- (3) Automatic integration of the digital twin into the optimization process. To the best of our knowledge, there is currently no existing framework that automatically integrates a digital twin into the layout design process.
- (4) Lightweight optimization framework in terms of the number of simulations required to converge to well-performing results.
- (5) We conducted proof-of-concept experiments on a use case of real-world size and complexity, using data from an actual factory operating real production processes.

This paper is organized as follows: After the introduction in Section 1, a formal definition of the problem addressed in this work is provided in Section 2. Section 3 surveys the related work. Then, the proposed method is described in Section 4. Section 5 presents the experiments and discusses the results obtained. Finally, Section 6 concludes the paper.

2 PROBLEM DEFINITION

In this work, we address an extended variant of the FLP that introduces important aspects often considered in practical applications of the FLP within manufacturing system design. We adopt the basic FLP elements definitions from [16]. The input includes a hall defined as an orthogonal polygon whose shape may be either convex or concave, see Figure 1. The following elements are specified for the hall:

- Technology area – the only area where workstations may be placed.
- Obstacles – areas where no workstation may be placed.
- Storages – devoted areas to store material, parts, and final products. Each storage has defined its entry point.
- Aisles – existing service and material handling aisles.
- Sectors – one or more disjoint logical sectors, which together cover the entire usable area of the hall.

Furthermore, a set of workstations is defined, with each workstation specified by the following attributes, see Figure 1:

- Work area – area of a rectangular shape that contains the technology of the given station.
- Handling zones – rectangular area(s) attached to sides of the working area.
- Input/output points – entry points that serve as interfaces between the workstation and its external environment, i.e., the points through which the workstation receives/sends the

material and products from/to other units of the production system.

- Available sectors – one or more logical sectors the workstation can be assigned to.

Figure 1: Definition of an empty production hall (left) and a workstation (right).

An important part of the problem specification is defining the production parameters required to simulate the manufacturing process for candidate production hall layouts. In this work, we consider the following:

- product portfolio – the products to be manufactured. Each product has a defined manufacturing process (workflow), including the types of workstations it must visit and the processing time required at each workstation.
- timespan – time window for which products will be manufactured.
- work flow – each workstation is assigned a set of potential supplier and receiver workstations. These links are based on the technological process of the products. Each workstation is assigned a set of potential supplier and receiver workstations. These links are derived from the technological processes of the products. A supplier communicates with a given workstation via its output point, while a receiver obtains the workstation's output via its input point. In this way, dependencies among workstations are defined. The production of a given product can be realized through multiple alternative routes across the production lines, with several instances of each line type potentially present in the production hall.

The objective is to optimally place all workstations within the production hall while satisfying a given set of constraints. Each workstation can be placed in the floorplan in one of eight possible orientations, including mirroring.

Here, we consider a primary optimization objective, denoted *Intensity*, aimed at minimizing the total transportation workload. This objective is evaluated using data obtained from a simulation of the production process over a specified time span. For each pair of dependent units—namely, workstation–workstation and workstation–storage pairs—a route intensity is computed as the product of the route length and the number of trips performed along that route. The objective *Intensity* is then defined as the sum of the transportation intensities over all routes in the production system.

In addition to the classical constraint requiring non-overlapping production lines, we consider the following constraints:

- (1) No workstation may occupy, even partially, any main handling aisle of the hall.
- (2) A minimum width for handling aisles is defined. This requirement applies both to the main aisles specified in the problem definition and to the aisles that emerge after all workstations are placed in the hall. Consequently, transportation between any two production units must be possible via aisles that satisfy the minimum width requirement along their entire length.
- (3) All input and output points of each workstation must be reachable from at least one main handling aisle via handling aisles that satisfy the minimum width requirement.
- (4) Each workstation may be placed only within one of the predefined sectors assigned to it.

3 RELATED WORK

Numerous formulations of the Facility Layout Problem have been proposed and investigated in the literature. These variants are typically classified according to key characteristics, including static versus dynamic layouts, single-objective versus multi-objective optimization, single-floor versus multi-floor configurations, and equal versus unequal facility area assignments, among others [1, 8, 20]. Facilities are typically categorized by shape and dimensions into two types: those with regular rectangular shapes and those with irregular, generally polygonal shapes [19].

Layout problems are generally known to be NP-hard, meaning that no exact algorithm can guarantee an optimal solution within reasonable polynomial time. On one hand, numerous studies have successfully applied mathematical programming approaches to specific FLP variants. For example, discrete quadratic assignment problem models have been used for FLP with regular-shaped, equal-area facilities [15, 17], while continuous linear and nonlinear mixed-integer programming models have addressed FLP involving irregularly shaped facilities with unequal areas [3, 7, 14, 25]. On the other hand, such approaches are applicable only to relatively small instances, typically involving no more than a few tens of facilities.

Comprehensive reviews of DT research and applications in industry are provided in [2, 23]. They outline key enabling technologies (e.g., modeling, simulation, data fusion) and major use cases from product design to prognostics and health management, and discusses current challenges (like the need for unified DT modeling) along with future research directions. In [4], two logistics schemes are compared using Tecnomatix Plant Simulation, demonstrating the value of DT technology for industrial layout and logistics decision-making. [6] proposes a digital-twin-based workshop layout optimization method that integrates real-time data fusion across the physical, digital, and fusion layers. The approach is validated on a welding shop, demonstrating increased capacity and reduced work-in-progress and tooling requirements. [18] introduces an approach for cost-focused industrial project design that integrates Tecnomatix Plant Simulation, visTABLE layout planning, and HELIOS iNuvio ERP. The approach does not implement an automatic optimization process. Instead, it follows a variant-simulation-cost selection approach where the layout variants are prepared in visTABLE, their performance is evaluated using Tecnomatix Plant Simulation, and their costs are assessed in the ERP

system. The “optimal” variant is selected by comparing the resulting metrics. [9] uses Tecnomatix Plant Simulation as a digital twin of a factory to evaluate processes and logistics safety. The DT runs scenario analyses, computes KPIs (throughput, cycle time, utilization), reveals bottlenecks (e.g., rework delays), and supports design-stage decisions on layout, workflows, and safety measures. [11] builds a dynamic and interactive virtual Industry 4.0 factory to support facility layout planning. It visualizes layouts and operations, simulates scenarios, detects bottlenecks and robot reachability/collisions, and tests intra-logistics policies. It enables interactive design decisions and data for deeper discrete even simulation-based analysis. No explicit optimization is implemented.

The work most closely related to our approach is introduced in [12, 13]. On one hand, it directly integrates a discrete-event simulation (DES) of the material-flow as a DT within a reinforcement learning (RL) environment for factory layout planning. In particular, the Double Deep Q-Learning (DDQN) agent is trained to allocate the functional units sequentially in the factory layout by minimizing the total throughput time calculated by DES of the material flow. This approach has the following limitations:

- It assumes the layout is divided into a grid with $n = 4 \times n_x \times n_y$ positions, with n_x and n_y positions in x-direction and y-direction, respectively, and 4 possible rotational states. To reduce the computational complexity of the RL approach, it implements the agent as the multi-discrete agent. However, the size of the action space remains $n_x + n_y + 4$. For real-world scenarios where n_x and n_y are significantly larger, this leads to a substantial increase in the size of the action space, which has a substantial impact on the convergence speed of the DDQN algorithm.
- The approach assumes a linear production workflow (i.e., process chain), where each functional unit has only one predecessor unit.
In contrast, our approach can also be applied to production scenarios where the workflow is represented as a general graph, meaning that each workstation may have multiple input and multiple output stations. Moreover, each workstation can be used multiple times within a single simulation, and each production task is assigned a set of workstations that can be used to perform the task.
- Even for the small optimization scenarios considered in [12, 13], this approach requires 5,000–7,500 training episodes for greenfield and around 70,000 episodes for brownfield scenarios to converge to well-performing solutions. Given that each episode involves a full simulation of the production system, the approach can be considered highly resource-intensive.

4 METHOD

In this section, we describe the proposed Digital Twin-based Evolutionary Facility Layout Algorithm (DT-EFLA). We begin by describing the main features of the evolutionary algorithm. Then, we describe aspects related to the automatic mapping of layouts to digital twins.

Figure 2: Illustration of the genotype-phenotype mapping process. The workstations are processed in the order defined by the priority list chromosome. The hall is gradually filled from top to bottom.

4.1 Evolutionary Optimization Algorithm

The evolutionary algorithm implemented in this work adopts the indirect representation of evolved floorplans introduced in [16]. In this representation, the exact position and orientation of the workstations are not explicitly encoded in the solution. Instead, the solution is represented using a *priority list*, which determines the order in which individual workstations will be added to the floorplan. This means that when evaluating the quality of a particular candidate solution, its chromosome (i.e., the priority list) must first be translated into the floorplan via an iterative mapping process that starts with an empty floorplan to which the workstations are incrementally added one by one in the order defined by the priority list; see Figure 2.

Two *heuristic insertion strategies* are used to determine the specific position of each newly placed workstation. These strategies gradually fill the available space in the top-to-bottom and either left-to-right or right-to-left manner. The process of transforming the priority list into a floorplan ends when all workstations have successfully been placed in the hall or when there is no longer sufficient space to accommodate the currently processed workstation. In the first case, mapping the genotype to the phenotype ends with a generated floorplan in which all workstations are placed in the hall, and the non-overlap constraint is satisfied. In the second case, an incomplete floorplan is generated and the solution is discarded. A significant advantage of this indirect representation is that simple genetic operators, crossover and mutation, can be used while ensuring that only solutions valid with respect to the non-overlap constraint are generated.

Here, we adopt the 2-point crossover operator as used in [16]. It is a variation of the standard order-based crossover that randomly selects two crossover points, inherits the head and tail sections from the first parent’s priority list, and fills in the middle section with the missing elements in the order they appear in the second parent’s priority list. The mutation operator operates on a single parent’s priority list so that it either changes the position of a randomly chosen workstation within the priority list or changes the way the workstation is added to the floor plan, i.e., its orientation or the insertion heuristic to be applied to the workstation.

In addition to the primary objective *Intensity*, the following auxiliary optimization criteria are used during the optimization process:

- *ManhattanDist* – This objective minimizes the total length of all connections between dependent workstations calculated as the sum of Manhattan distances between the output point of the source workstation and the input point of the destination workstation over all pairs of interconnected workstations. We chose the Manhattan distance because it better reflects actual conditions in a production hall, where transportation between stations is typically carried out via a network of orthogonal pathways and conveyor belts. Note that this metric serves only as a proxy for estimating the actual distances between production lines. Nevertheless, it provides at least a coarse estimate of the quality of workstation placement within the production hall, as their proximity serves as a meaningful indicator of how demanding the manufacturing process will be in terms of part and product transportation. A key advantage of this criterion is that it is computationally far less demanding than simulating the manufacturing process within a digital twin.
- *SimulatedDist* – In a similar spirit, we define another additional criterion that already requires simulation in a digital twin mirroring the candidate layout. However, only light-weight simulations are performed, as the digital twin is used solely to obtain a more accurate estimate of the transportation time between individual workstations. Specifically, for each pair of dependent workstations, the shortest feasible route is identified and its traversal time is simulated. The resulting value of this criterion is defined as the sum of all such contributions. Importantly, this criterion is again computationally much less expensive than a full-scale simulation of the entire manufacturing process over a longer time horizon.
- *Inaccessibility* – This criterion is designed to strengthen the optimization pressure toward solutions that are feasible in terms of the accessibility of all workstations and their input and output points. In practice, random genetic operators frequently generate solutions that are infeasible because some production lines are inaccessible. Figure 3 illustrates this situation with an example of a layout with three enclosed areas to which no access aisles lead. If a workstation has its input/output point located on the boundary of such an area, this contact point becomes inaccessible, rendering the workstation unusable. This objective minimizes the number of input/output points that cannot be accessed via any path directly connected to some of the hall’s communication aisles. Using this criterion, the MOEA is guided towards the solutions with all workstations fully accessible from the main internal aisles of the production hall.

Note that the *Intensity* and *SimulatedDist* criteria are calculated only when the *Inaccessibility* criterion is zero, i.e., when all workstations are fully accessible, allowing the entire production process to be simulated. First, the collision-free floorplan is converted into an internal representation in Plant Simulation, where the production process is subsequently simulated over a selected time period (see Figure 4). Here, we use a two-month interval,

Figure 3: An example of a floorplan with inaccessible areas (highlighted in red), along whose boundaries lie the input/output points of several workstations.

Figure 4: Evaluation workflow using the Plant Simulation.

which is sufficient for all significant effects resulting from the proposed workstation layout to manifest. Floorplans with a non-zero *Inaccessibility* value are assigned a positive infinite value for this criterion.

This evolutionary algorithm primarily optimizes *Intensity* as its main objective and is therefore essentially single-objective. Nevertheless, it also exhibits elements of multi-objective optimization, specifically in the implementation of the operator used to compare two solutions. In this comparison, the criteria are assigned priorities ordered from lowest to highest as follows: *ManhattanDist* → *Inaccessibility* → *SimulatedDist* → *Intensity*. The comparison outcome is determined by the priority and value of the most significant criterion available. The following situations may occur:

- Both solutions have a computed *Intensity* value: the solution with the better *Intensity* value is preferred, regardless of the other criteria.
- One solution has a computed *Intensity* value, while the other does not; the former is preferred, irrespective of all criteria values.
- One solution has a computed *SimulatedDist* value, while the other has only *ManhattanDist*: the former solution is preferred, again regardless of the absolute criterion values.

Algorithm 1: DT-EFLA

Input: POPSIZE ... population size
 MAXGENS ... maximum number of generations
 n_f ... nb. of generations between full simulations

Output: best evolved layout

```

1 pop.init(ManhattanDist, Inaccessibility);
2 gen ← 0
3 while gen < MAXGENS do
4   interpop ← breed(pop)
5   for ind in interpop do
6     if ind.collisionFree() then
7       if gen %  $n_f$  then
8         ind.evaluate(Intensity)
9       else
10        ind.evaluate(SimulatedDist)
11      else
12        ind.evaluate(ManhattanDist, Inaccessibility)
13    merge(pop, interpop)
14    gen ← gen + 1
15 return selectBest(pop)

```

- Both solutions have ManhattanDist as the most important computed objective value, along with the Inaccessibility value. The solution with the smaller Inaccessibility value is preferred; in case of a tie, the one with the better value of ManhattanDist is selected.

The overall procedure of the DT-EFLA is shown in Algorithm 1. The algorithm begins by initializing a population of candidate solutions. This step involves randomly generating priority lists for each individual and computing their objective values, ManhattanDist and Inaccessibility. Then, the population evolves over a predefined number of generations. First, an intermediate population of new solutions, interpop, is created using crossover and mutation operators applied with specified rates. All individuals in interpop are then evaluated based on their feasibility. If an individual is collision-free, it proceeds to simulation in the digital twin. Every n_f generations, it undergoes full simulation, resulting in the computation of the Intensity value. In intermediate generations, only the SimulatedDist value is calculated. Infeasible individuals are evaluated using only ManhattanDist and Inaccessibility. Subsequently, the intermediate and current populations are merged to form the next generation, based on the comparison rule described above. Finally, the best solution with respect to Intensity is returned from the final population.

4.2 Simulation-based layout testing

Simulating production in the digital twin of the manufacturing hall, based on a candidate layout proposed by the evolutionary algorithm, involves several preparatory steps and the configuration of many parameters. First, the structure of the production area (i.e., the main outline of the shop floor) is defined, and the primary material handling aisles are established. Next, the proposed positions of workstations and their connection points to the material handling

routes are registered. Finally, all unoccupied areas that may serve as communication zones are identified.

The simulation itself is executed using the model, which defines, among other things, the technological processes, workstation processing times (both fixed and statistically distributed), operation or product defect rates, material-handling resources and their parameters (e.g., number of vehicles, capacity, speed, and admissible routes), product generation strategies, including arrival frequency, batch sizes, and the proportions of different product types. During the simulation, whenever a step from a station of type A to a station of type B is required, the closest currently available station of type B is selected. Products that cannot be assigned to any available workstation are transported to the work-in-process (WIP) buffer. Importantly, all of this is handled automatically within our framework, without any user interaction.

5 EXPERIMENTS

5.1 Data and Experiment Set Up

The proposed method is tested on a use case based on a real production system designed to process two types of products, which pass through eight types of workstations, see Figure 5. The technological processes consist of 10 and 14 steps, respectively, with certain workstations being revisited multiple times. Due to capacity constraints, selected workstation types are duplicated within the production system, with up to 10 instances per type. Transportation is handled by automated guided vehicles (AGVs), which imposes an additional hard constraint on the generated layouts: a minimum aisle width must be ensured to guarantee accessibility to all input and output points of every workstation. During the production process, storage facilities are used for raw materials, work-in-progress items, and finished goods. Each simulation run is executed over a 30-day horizon, which is sufficient for the manufacturing system to reach steady-state conditions.

The primary output of the simulation is the Intensity value. Nevertheless, the simulation also tracks additional statistics, such as AGV utilization, warehouse utilization, and workstation utilization. These metrics and measures can be used for a detailed assessment of the quality of the proposed solutions from various perspectives.

The proposed algorithm was tested using the following settings of its main parameters:

- POPSIZE: 50
- MAXGENS: 300
- n_f : 4

5.2 Results

We conducted a series of ten independent runs for each of the following scenarios:

- a scenario considering a production hall with a single sector,
- a scenario for a hall with two sectors,
- a brownfield scenario with 12 workstations having fixed positions,
- a single-sector scenario in which no simulations are used during the optimization; the computation is driven solely by the proxy metrics ManhattanDist and Inaccessibility.

Figure 5: Graph with a technological process of the two products, A and B.

Tables 1–3 report the median values of the optimization criteria observed for the three best solutions in each run.

Table 1: Results obtained for the single-sector scenario.

n th best	ManhattanDist	SimulatedDist	Intensity
1	14280	15146	4159579
2	14106	14972	4222602
3	14242	15108	4248315

Table 2: Results obtained for the scenario with the hall divided into two sectors.

n th best	ManhattanDist	SimulatedDist	Intensity
1	13285	14151	3868794
2	13432	14299	3924365
3	13254	14120	3941180

Table 3: Results obtained for the brownfield scenario with 12 workstations anchored at a fixed position.

n th best	ManhattanDist	SimulatedDist	Intensity
1	12791	13658	3711533
2	12914	13781	3723804
3	13084	13951	3731822

Table 4 presents the median values obtained from ten experimental runs in which no simulations are used during the computation.

Table 4: Results obtained for the single-sector scenario where the optimization process was guided only by Inaccessibility and ManhattanDist metrics. Only the final solutions were simulated using simAll.

metric best	min	median	max
ManhattanDist	11056	11078	11104
Intensity	4148380	4944079	5347371

Figure 6 shows the relationship between the ManhattanDist and Intensity performance metrics. The data come from runs conducted within the single-sector experiment.

Figure 6: Correlation between parameters ManhattanDist and Intensity (left) and SimulatedDist and Intensity (right).

Figure 7 illustrates the convergence of Intensity during the computation for the single-sector experiment. Figure 8 shows an example of the best solution found for the single-sector scenario. Figure 9 shows an example of the best solution found for the two-sectors scenario. Figure 10 shows an example of the best solution found for the brownfield scenario.

5.3 Discussion

Figure 6 presents the relationship between the auxiliary optimization metrics ManhattanDist and SimulatedDist and the primary

Figure 7: Convergence of Intensity over generations, shown for individual runs and for the median best-so-far value across ten independent runs.

Figure 8: Single-sector scenario solution example.

Figure 9: Two-sectors scenario solution example.

Figure 10: Brownfield scenario solution example.

metric *Intensity*. As expected, the *SimulatedDist* metric correlates much more strongly with *Intensity* than the *ManhattanDist* metric.

The results of the experiment conducted without the use of simulations are particularly interesting. This experimental scenario was designed to test whether high-quality solutions in terms of *Intensity* can be achieved using only the *Inaccessibility* and *ManhattanDist* optimization criteria. In other words, it examines whether it is necessary to simulate candidate solutions during the search and guide the computation towards promising areas of the search space based on simulated performance metrics.

We conducted a series of runs in which neither of the two types of simulations, *simDist* and *simAll*, was performed during the search. Only the best conflict-free solutions found at the end of the runs were simulated using *simAll* to obtain their *Intensity* performance values. Table 4 presents summary statistics computed from the results of the five experiments described above. The values in the *ManhattanDist* row show that the evolutionary algorithm achieved significantly better outcomes with respect to this performance criterion, compared to the results in Table 1. In contrast, the values in the *Intensity* row are considerably worse than those in Table 1. This clearly demonstrates the importance of simulating candidate solutions during the optimization process.

Statistics on the number of evaluations of *SimulatedDist* and *Intensity* performed during the computation are also particularly interesting. In the former case, the counts are in the low hundreds, whereas in the latter case they are in the higher tens.

6 CONCLUSIONS

This paper presented a novel framework for solving the Facility Layout Problem by tightly integrating an evolutionary optimization algorithm with digital twin simulations. Unlike traditional FLP approaches based on static evaluation models, the proposed method leverages automatically generated digital twins to assess candidate layouts using dynamic, simulation-based performance metrics.

The framework enables asynchronous, fully automated exploration of layout alternatives while respecting practical constraints such as non-overlapping workstations, accessibility requirements, and sector-wise placement restrictions.

By combining feasibility checks, lightweight proxy criteria, and progressively more accurate simulation-based evaluations, this approach achieves an effective balance between computational efficiency and solution quality.

Experimental validation on a real-world-inspired production system demonstrated that the proposed approach can reliably generate high-performing layouts while requiring only a limited number of full production simulations. The results highlight the importance of simulation-guided optimization: experiments conducted without simulation-based criteria produced significantly inferior layouts in terms of transportation workload.

At the same time, the strong correlation observed between the lightweight proxy metric *SimulatedDist* and the primary objective *Intensity* confirms the usefulness of proxy-based guidance in reducing computational effort.

Overall, the proposed framework shows strong potential for practical deployment in industrial layout design, providing a scalable and automated alternative to labor-intensive manual processes. Future work will focus on extending the approach to additional performance objectives, uncertainty-aware simulations, and more complex manufacturing scenarios.

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